

**PLACE AND ROLE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE GENERAL SYSTEM
OF EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN****Khodzhanov Aziz Rakhimovich****Associate Professor of the Department of "Physical Education and Sports",
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The article analyzes the place and role of physical culture in the general system of upbringing of preschool children. Usually, in physical education classes, a child, acting with objects, masters their physical properties, learns to control their movement in space, begins to coordinate their movements, based on mastering speech, beginnings of controlling their own behavior appear. At present, the analysis of the place and role of physical culture in the general system of upbringing of preschool children is widely presented. Every parent wants to see their baby healthy, cheerful, well physically developed. Along with the completely natural concern for the purity of his body, satisfying the needs for food, it is extremely necessary to provide the need for movement.

Key words: physical culture, methodology, theory, tactics, technique, activity, formation, development.

From the moment of birth, a normally developing child strives for movement. In the beginning, these movements are disordered. However, they are gradually beginning to acquire a more coordinated and focused character. The formation of this need, which is important for life, largely depends on the characteristics of life and upbringing, on how the adults around the child create the necessary conditions, contribute to the timely development of movements that are accessible by age. Movements have a comprehensive effect on the human body, and this effect is immeasurably higher for a growing and developing child's body [1].

Raising the need for children to move every day, do physical exercises from an early age, you can lay solid foundations for good health, harmonious development of the child. Physical education is closely related to the age characteristics of children [2].

In this regard, specific tasks, content, methods and forms of organization of physical education in early preschool and school age are determined, as well as the successive relationship between them. Physical education is especially important in early and preschool

childhood, when the most intensive development of the child's body takes place, when its main movements are formed, but at the same time the body is still very weak and vulnerable. Physical education of preschool children is aimed primarily at protecting life and strengthening health, full-fledged physical development, the formation of motor skills and the development of physical qualities, at the development of cultural and hygienic skills, and the cultivation of habits for an orderly rhythm of life. In physical education classes, a child, acting with objects, masters their physical properties, learns to control their movement in space, begins to coordinate their movements, on the basis of mastering speech, the beginnings of controlling their own behavior appear. The importance of physical education is spoken of in the works of outstanding teachers: Ya.A. Komensky, E.A. Pokrovsky, P.F. Lesgaft, K.D. Ushinsky, A.S. Makarenko. The importance of the purposefulness of the organization of work on physical education was noted by such scientists as Yu.F. Zmanovsky, V.A. Kudryavtseva, V.G. Alyamovskaya, A.A. Ukhtomsky, N.A. Bernshtein, A.V. Zaporozhets, A.N. Leontiev, S.L. Rubinstein. Modern living conditions contribute to a decrease in the physical activity of children. Recently, teachers of preschool institutions are concerned not only with low physical activity, but also with the state of health of children [3].

It is known that it is already in children's health adolescents. Preschool education is faced with the task of protecting and strengthening the health of children [4].

as well as the use of new forms for organizing circle activities in physical education in a preschool institution. Caring for children, their well-being, happiness and health has always been and will be the main concern of adults. In turn, parents, teachers and coaches must find the optimal types of physical activity to successfully strengthen the health of children and familiarize the child with regular physical education from the first days of life. Many researchers (Z.L. Venkova, T.E. Tokayeva, V.G. Alyamovskaya, Yu.F. Zmanovsky, T.I. its normal formation and development. Another effective method of increasing the effectiveness of physical culture and health-improving work of children's educational institutions, according to V.G. Alyamovskaya, N. Efimenko, K.K. Utrobina is the introduction of new pedagogical technologies. An excellent means of preventing overwork and optimizing the motor activity of children who experience a negative effect during static loads is the use of elements of oriental techniques in physical culture lessons and yoga circle classes. An essential aspect of the influence of asanas (yoga postures) is an increase in emotional tone. During classes, the child's mood improves, a feeling of joy and pleasure appears. Asanas with the correct psychological and pedagogical approach are a powerful optimizing factor. The main goal of yoga classes for children is the formation of a

positive and sustainable interest in physical activity. Mastering yoga asanas will help the natural development of the child's body, create the necessary, individual motor regime and a positive psychological attitude. All this contributes to the strengthening of health, physical and mental development. The tasks set by the parents of practicing yoga By their nature, they are very receptive and able to get real joy from yoga. They are very mobile, but equally fragile. They enjoy trying a wide variety of challenging poses and movements. The system of physical education in preschool institutions is a unity of purpose, objectives, means, forms and methods of work aimed at strengthening the health and all-round physical development of children [5].

It is at the same time a subsystem, part of the national system of physical education, which, in addition to these components, also includes institutions and organizations that carry out and control physical education. Each institution, depending on its specifics, has its own specific areas of work that meet the general state and national interests [6].

The system of physical education in preschool institutions is built taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of children. The goal of physical education is to develop a healthy lifestyle in children. In the process of physical education, health-improving, educational and educational tasks are carried out. Allocation of three groups of tasks makes it possible to more purposefully build work on the physical education of preschoolers. Wellness tasks. Wellness goals have life-sustaining meaning. Health, and often the life of a person depends on their successful solution. Protection of life and health promotion, improvement of physical development, functional improvement and increasing the efficiency of the child's body, as well as hardening are priority tasks. This is due to the fact that the organs and functional systems of preschoolers are still imperfect, the protective properties of the body are poorly developed, children are more susceptible to unfavorable environmental conditions, and are more likely to get sick [7].

Taking into account the specifics of age, the tasks are determined in a more specific form: to help the formation of the curvature of the spine, the development of the arches of the foot, and the strengthening of the ligamentous-articular apparatus. Promote the development of all muscle groups, especially the extensor muscles; the correct ratio of body parts; contribute to the improvement of the activity of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, the correct functioning internal organs, the development of the function of thermoregulation, the central nervous system (to train the processes of excitation and inhibition, their mobility), the sense organs, the motor analyzer. The means of implementing the tasks of this group are hygienic and social factors, good nutrition, health-improving forces of nature, a rational mode of life, and

physical exercises. Pedagogical work aimed at solving this problem includes the organization of the children's regime of life, hardening procedures, and special exercises for the development of movements. This area of physical education of children requires the educator to have constant contacts with medical workers, taking into account their recommendations, an individual approach to children, and conversations with parents [8].

In the process of physical education of preschool children, it is necessary to solve educational tasks: the formation of motor skills and abilities, the development of physical qualities, the inculcation of the skills of correct posture, hygiene skills, the development of special knowledge [9].

Due to the plasticity of the nervous system, motor skills and abilities are formed relatively easily in children. Most of the movements (crawling, walking, running, skiing, cycling, etc.) are used by children in everyday life for movement, which facilitates communication with the environment and promotes knowledge of it. This is how children learn about the properties of water while swimming. Correct performance of physical exercises positively influences the development of throwing for distance in the way "from behind the back over the shoulder", performs a swing and throw with a greater amplitude of movement of the trunk, legs, arms, which contributes to better development of the corresponding muscles, ligaments and joints. Formed motor skills and abilities save physical strength. If the child does the exercise easily, without stress, then he spends less neuromuscular energy to perform it. Thanks to this, it is possible to repeat the exercise more times and to more effectively influence the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, as well as develop physical qualities [10].

The use of well-formed skills and abilities allows us to comprehend the tasks that arise in unforeseen situations in the process of motor, especially game, activity. So, a child, having learned how to jump in length with a running start, already thinks not about how to jump over the ditch in the game "Wolf in the Ditch", but about how best to escape from the wolf. In the process of developing skills and abilities, children develop the ability to easily master more complex movements and various types of activities, including these movements (labor operations). Motor skills and abilities formed in children under 7 years old form the foundation for their further improvement in school, facilitate the mastery of more complex movements and allow them to achieve high results in sports in the future. In preschool children, it is necessary to form the skills of performing basic gymnastics exercises (drill and general developmental exercises, basic movement), as well as sports exercises. In addition, children should be taught to play in sports games (tennis, badminton, towns), to perform elements of sports games

(volleyball, basketball, hockey, football, etc.). In preschool children, it is necessary to form the ability to maintain the correct body position when they sit, stand, walk. Correct posture is of great importance for the normal functioning of all internal organs and systems of the child's body. It largely depends on the development of the musculoskeletal system, but this is a skill that is important to form in a timely manner. In kindergarten and in the family, great attention should be paid to instilling skills and habits of personal and public hygiene (washing hands, going to the toilet before exercising, taking care of the cleanliness of the body, suit, shoes, toys, premises, etc.). The health of children largely depends on this. Preschool children need to be taught the available knowledge related to physical education. Children should know about the benefits of classes, about the importance of physical exercises and other means of physical education (hygienic conditions, natural factors of nature, physical labor). It is important that children have an idea of the technique of physical exercises and the methodology of their implementation, about the correct posture, and also know about the norms of personal and public hygiene. Children should know the name of body parts, the direction of movement (up, down, forward, backward, right, left, etc.). name and purpose of sports equipment, rules for storing and caring for it, rules for caring for clothes and shoes, etc. In the process of doing physical exercises, children also consolidate knowledge about the habits of animals, birds, insects, natural phenomena, and social life. The knowledge gained allows children to more consciously perform physical exercises and independently repeat them not only in kindergarten, but also at home. The amount of knowledge expands with the age of children. Thus, educational tasks provide for the formation of motor skills and abilities in children, the development of physical qualities, and the acquisition of elementary knowledge about their body by preschoolers; the role of physical exercise in his life, ways to strengthen his own health Here, the leading means are such as the model of an adult, the children's own activities, artistic means. The form of work, in the process of which the tasks are most adequately solved, is educational work in physical culture lessons and in everyday life. Among the main methods should be highlighted experimenting, exercise, conversation, viewing pictures and illustrations. Educational tasks. From an early age, it is necessary to educate children in the habit of strict adherence to the daily regimen and develop the need for daily exercise, develop the ability to independently engage in these exercises in kindergarten and at home. It is important to teach children how to organize and carry out physical exercises, including outdoor games, with their peers and toddlers. It is important to instill in children a love for sports, interest in the results of their activities and in the achievements of athletes. In the process of physical education, there are great opportunities for

the implementation of moral, mental, aesthetic, labor education. Well-organized physical education greatly contributes to the mental development of children, as it provides optimal conditions for the normal functioning of the nervous system and other body systems, which in turn helps better perception and memorization. In physical exercises, children develop all mental processes (perception, thinking, memory, imagination, etc.), as well as mental operations (observation, comparison, analysis, synthesis, generalization, etc.). It is necessary to strive for children to be able to creatively use the acquired knowledge and skills in their motor activity, showing activity, independence, ingenuity, resourcefulness. At the same time, it is important to bring up positive emotions that create a cheerful, cheerful mood, as well as develop the ability to quickly overcome a negative mental state. This is necessary because positive emotions have a beneficial effect on the work of all organs and systems of the body, provide the speed and strength of the formation of motor skills and abilities. Thus, educational tasks are aimed at the development of personality traits and the need for physical perfection. Of course, these tasks are closely related to health-improving tasks, since when they are solved, the child's personal qualities are also formed. The means of implementing this group of tasks are the activities of children, games, as well as artistic means (fiction, folklore, films, works of musical and visual arts). The work takes place in different forms: physical culture and health work in the daily routine (morning exercises, outdoor games, physical exercises for a walk), independent physical activity of children, active rest (physical education, holidays, health days). Exercise methods, conversation, play, problem situations creation, analysis of physical and moral qualities. It can be concluded that the purpose of physical education in a preschool institution is to promote the harmonious formation of a comprehensively developed personality. The main means for achieving this goal is the study of the foundations of personal physical culture by children, which means a certain amount of knowledge, skills and needs, the optimal level of health, physical development, diversified development of motor abilities, the ability to carry out proper motor, physical culture, health and sports activities. At the same time, it is necessary to purposefully work with children to educate value orientations for the physical and spiritual development of the individual, a healthy lifestyle, the formation of needs and desires for regular exercise and sports, the development of volitional moral qualities. The main means of studying physical culture is the child's mastering of its basic foundations, that is, the objectively necessary and obligatory level of physical culture for each person, without which it is impossible to effectively carry out life, regardless of what the child wants to do in the future. Physical education of preschoolers is a complex process. Mastering the technique physical exercises are

initially carried out at specially organized physical education, but later the child uses these movements in everyday life, in independent activity, therefore, the habit of acting in a certain way is successfully formed only with close interaction of the physical education teacher, the group teacher and the family. In order for this work to be effective, it is necessary to clearly understand what kind of return expected from each of them. Observance of a strict sequence is envisaged in the assimilation of the program by children, taking into account the age characteristics and the possibilities of the child at each period of his life, the state of the nervous system and the whole organism as a whole. Exceeding the requirements, accelerating the pace of teaching children, bypassing the intermediate links of the program, should be considered unacceptable, since this causes unbearable stress on the body, harming the health and neuropsychic development of children. Physical education at the same time comprehensively solves the problems of mental, moral, aesthetic and labor education. In all forms of organization of physical education of children (classes, outdoor games, independent physical activity, and so on), the attention of the head of physical education is directed to the upbringing of a consciously acting child, according to his age capabilities, who successfully masters motor skills, who is able to navigate in the environment, and actively overcome difficulties encountered. , showing a desire for creative searches. When conducting classes with preschoolers, physical exercises should be selected taking into account age physiology and in accordance with the characteristics of the age period of childhood, the nature of response reactions. To strengthen the health of children and prevent diseases, it is necessary not only to increase the level of their physical activity, but also to systematically carry out active hardening measures. They can be local and common, traditional or non-traditional. The theory of physical education of preschool children is continuously developing and enriched with new knowledge obtained as a result of research covering the diverse aspects of child education. Research data, verified in the mass practice of children's institutions, are introduced into programs, teaching aids, textbooks and practical work with children, contributing to the progress of all educational

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